

Mass propagation of Seabuckthorn (*Hippophae rhamnoides* L.) through shoot encapsulations

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Received: April 10, 2020 /Revised: April 17, 2020 /Accepted: June 29, 2020 /Published online: September 30, 2020
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Abstract

Biodiversity conservation is a primary goal of the conservationists around the world and it can be achievable through habitat conservation and plantation. The Himalaya is one of the Biodiversity Hotspot in the present world. Seabuckthorn has been pioneer plant species for his tremendous ecological and economical services as medicine, nutritional supplement, firewood, fencing, tree guard, wind break, building construction, religious rites, agricultural implements and soil fertility enhancement etc. The present perspective about advancing vegetative propagation of seabuckthorn and will have to develop a vegetative micro-propagation system from 1 year old growth stem cutting (1 mm diameter). These cutting further cut into 1-2 mm length and encapsulated with sodium alginate. Further these encapsulated beads will be regenerated to form saplings on MS growth media/simple peat moss/perlite media. Further these regenerated saplings will be made available to direct field plantation. I think, above modification to the vegetative propagation method can be boon for the seabuckthorn conservationists and plantation in the Western Trans Himalayan Landscape of the India.

Keywords: Seabuckthorn; Trans Himalaya; Biodiversity Conservation; Micro-encapsulation; *Hippophae*

Biodiversity conservation is a primary goal of the conservationists around the world and it can be achievable through habitat conservation and plantation. The Himalaya is one of the Biodiversity Hotspot in the present world (Roy & Kushwaha, 2018). Recently it is known that seabuckthorn conserve the plant diversity in the Himalayas (Kumar, 2018). Western Himalayan biodiversity, especially in Leh-Ladakh, has been dependent on coexistence of seabuckthorn species in the Leh and Nubra Vallies of Ladakh (Korekar, Sharma, et al., 2012; Korekar, Dolkar, Singh, Srivastava, & Stobdan, 2014; Korekar, Dwivedi, Singh, Srivastava, & Stobdan, 2013). Natural seabuckthorn forests is limited to

revierine and sacrete grooves of the vallies. Seabuckthorn has been pioneer plant species for his tremendous ecological and economical services as medicine, nutritional supplement, firewood, fencing, tree guard, wind break, building construction, religious rites, agricultural implements and soil fertility enhancement etc (Korekar, Sharma, et al., 2012; Korekar et al., 2014, 2013; Korekar, Singh, Srivastava, & Stobdan, 2012; Stobdan et al., 2010). Recent interest in the vegetative propagation of seabuckthorn arises primarily because of there is increasing demand of seabuckthorn for economical as well as ecological point of view as it has tremendous potential to fix the atmospheric nitrogen and enhanced the soil fertility (Dolkar, Dolkar, Angmo, Srivastava, & Stobdan, 2016; Korekar et al., 2014). With vegetative propagation methods, the produced offspring is genetically identical to the stock

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plant. Hardwood cuttings are more often used in propagation of deciduous woody plants as it is one of the cheapest and easiest method of vegetative propagation. Typically, they require less or no special equipment during rooting, which can be readily performed in nurseries. Vegetative propagation through pencil thickness hardwood cutting is the method of choice for propagation of seabuckthorn. Currently, there is a lot of information concerning the propagation of pencil thickness (5-10 mm diameter and 2-3 diameter) hardwood stem cuttings from seabuckthorn (Dolkar et al., 2016). However, propagation by these thickness hardwood cutting results in fewer cuttings per plant. Besides, rooting success rate through pencil thickness cutting is low. Micropropagation of seabuckthorn is possible but it requires high-tech facilities and well-trained personnel, which is lacking in most places where seabuckthorn can be grown. Micro-encapsulation of micro-cuttings has been demonstrated the significant good results in some woody plants (Piccioni & Standardi, 1995; Rathore & Kheni, 2017). These studies encourage me to develop a advanced vegetative propagation methods for seabuckthorn using micro-encapsulations (Piccioni & Standardi, 1995) and vegetative propagation (Dolkar et al., 2016) to get large number of saplings for mass plantation in Western Himalayan Landscape. Therefore, the present study will have to develop a vegetative micro-propagation system from 1 year old growth stem cutting (1 mm diameter). These cutting further cut into 1-2 mm length and encapsulated with sodium alginate. Further these encapsulated beads will be regenerated to form saplings on MS growth media/simple peat moss/perlite media. Further these regenerated saplings will be made available to direct field plantation.

This can be achieved through some modification protocol of Piccioni et al; Rathore et al and Dolkar et al (Dolkar et al., 2016; Piccioni & Standardi, 1995; Rathore & Kheni, 2017). In brief, the micro-cuttings viz. Seabuckthorn shoot (2-4 mm) of 1 year old shoots will be excised aseptically from seabuckthorn plant and these micro-cuttings will be used for encapsulation. Different combinations of 1.0-5.0 % sodium alginate (Na-alginate) and 50-200 mM calcium chloride (CaCl₂.2H₂O) prepared in distilled water or liquid MS medium will be evaluated as suitable matrix for encapsulation of micro-cuttings. Both the gel matrix and complexation agent were

steamsterilized at 121 C and 15 psi for 15 min. For encapsulation, the micro-cuttings will be dropped in gel matrix for 3-5 min to allow their covering by gel. Then the droplets of gel matrix each containing a single micro-cutting were dropped in complexing agent and allowed for polymerization and formation of capsules for 30 min. Alginate capsules with micro-cuttings will be collected, washed and soaked with sterile whattman filter paper. Alternatively the base of micro-cuttings was pulse-treated with 1.23, 2.46 and 4.92 M indole-3-butyric acid (IBA) for 1-3 min and subsequently encapsulated. This encapsulates will be stored at 4.0 ± 0.5 C for different time period (0-60) under sterile conditions. The encapsulates were inoculated on 0.75 % agar gelled full or with strength of MS medium supplemented with 0, 1.11, 2.22 and 4.44 M BAP along with 0.57 M IAA and incubated in a aseptic room for plantlet regeneration. Alternatively encapsulates were inoculated on sterile media like peat moss/perlite/soil in polythene bags for direct conversion of encapsulates into plantlets. The polythene bags will be covered with inverted polythene bags to maintain high RH and nutrified with strength of MS macro-salt solution.

We think, above modification to the vegetative propagation method can be boon for the seabuckthorn conservationists and plantation in the Western Trans Himalayan Landscape of the India.

Acknowledgments:

The authors are thankful to Director DIHAR, DRDO and Dr. T. Stobdan, Senior Scientist, DIHAR, DRDO for kind support during the institutional visit.

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Competing interests

The author is a founder of Chetnagiri Biotech LLP. The author declares no other competing financial interest.

Additional information

No Additional information is available for this paper

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